

GROWTH PERFORMANCE AND CARCASS CHARACTERISTICS OF WEST AFRICAN DWARF (WAD) GOATS FED OIL PALM LEAF MEAL – CASSAVA PEEL BASED DIETS

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ABSTRACT

An 8 week experiment was conducted at Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike Livestock Farm Unit to determine the effects of oil palm leaf meal – cassava peel based diets on growth performance and carcass evaluation of West African Dwarf (WAD) goats. Nine weaner bucks aged 6-8 months and averaging 8.0kg in weight were divided into 3 groups of 3 and each group randomly assigned to one of the treatments in a Completely Randomized Design. The three treatments (I, II and III) were formulated to contain 0, 15 and 30% oil palm leaf meal respectively. Animals in each treatment were fed respective diets for 60days. Parameters measured were feed intake, body weight gain (BWG), feed conversion ratio (FCR) and dressing percentage. Feed intake was 367.40, 367.00 and 394.20g/d for treatments I, II and III, respectively. The values were significantly different ($P<0.05$). The goats on treatment III had the least feed conversion ratio (9.00) which was significantly different ($P<0.05$) from the goats on treatment II (10.83) and those on treatment I (12.33). Bodyweight gain was highest for goats on treatment III (44.23kg) which was significantly different from those on treatment II (34.03kg) and treatment I (30.60kg). Dressing percentage values were significantly different ($P<0.05$) among the treatment groups with the highest for goats on treatment III. Treatment III therefore appear to be a better fattening diet since it had a better FCR, BWG and dressing percentage.

Key words: Feed intake, body weight gain, feed conversion ratio, dressing percentage, goats, oil palm.

INTRODUCTION

Ruminant animal production in the tropics is faced with seasonal fluctuations in feed material especially in dry season (Oluwatomi2010). The available forages are of low quality hence there is marked decrease in voluntary feed intake and digestibility of ruminants and goats in particular. In Nigeria food competition exists between humans and livestock for the conventional feedstuffs (maize, wheat, rice etc). As a result, these feedstuffs become scarce and very exorbitant when available. The ever increasing livestock population in Nigeria therefore calls for alternative sources of feed materials to boost livestock population. This fodder instability has led to the search for cheap sources of energy and protein to supplements the low quality forage during the dry season. These supplements should be cheap, readily available and mostly of little or no importance to man (Amaefule 2002). Cassava peels and oil palm leaves are both farm wastes of great importance in Nigeria. Cassava peel is a major by-product of cassava tuberous root processing industry. It is largely underutilized with an annual production of about 32million metric tonnes (FAO 2005). Oil palm is a plant that produces many by-product used by the animal feed industry. Recently, oil palm leaf or frond has been identified as a potential feed for ruminants and other herbivores (Islam 1999; Esonu *et al.* 2008).

This study therefore, was aimed at evaluating the effect of oil palm leaf meal – cassava peel based diets on the growth performance and carcass characteristics of West African Dwarf goats.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The cassava peels used for this trial were collected from the Garri processing unit of National Root Crops Research Institute, Umudike, Abia State and sun-dried on a concrete floor for 3-5days depending on the intensity of the sun. The sun-dried cassava peels were then milled and bagged for feed formulation. The oil palm leaves were harvested from the oil palm trees around the bushes within Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike and the neighbouring communities. The stalks were removed and the leaves were chopped to facilitate sun-drying for 4days until they become crispy while still retaining the green colouration. After sun-drying, they were milled and bagged for feed formulation.

Feeding Trial

Nine WAD bucks aged 6-8 months and weighing between 7-10 kg were quarantined for 21 days, dewormed and treated with appropriate acaricides. Each animal was later housed individually in a well ventilated cement floored pen equipped with feeding and watering troughs. The animals underwent a 21 day preliminary period of adjustment to accustom them to the new environment. All the animals were weighed and divided into three groups of three animals each. The three experimental diets (Table 1) were randomly allotted to the three animal groups. Each animal within a group received 1 kg daily of the assigned treatment feed for 60 days. Portable drinking water was provided for each animal *ad libitum*. Voluntary feed intake was determined daily for each animal by subtracting the feed refusals from daily feed served. Daily feed intake and weekly weight were recorded for each animal.

Slaughter Technique

The slaughter technique was carried out according to Ukanwoko (2007). The goats were starved for 24 hours before slaughter. They were weighed just before slaughter, after slaughter and after dressing. Dressing percentage was calculated as the weight of dressed warm carcass in relation to bodyweight before slaughter. A dressed (warm) carcass is defined as the weight of the animal less the head, skin thoracic contents and pelvic cavities (including the diaphragm and kidney) and the limbs distal to the copal and tarsal joints. The heart, the liver less the gall bladder, the lungs, the spleen, the pelvic fat and the four feet were weighed using the scientific weighing scale. The gut was weighed full and empty.

Analytical Procedure

The feeding trial was a Completely Randomized Design Experiment. Data obtained were analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) procedures (Steel and Torrie 1980). Where ANOVA detected significant treatment effects, means were separated using Duncan's multiple range test procedure of SAS,(). Meat cuts, offal weights and organ weights were expressed as percentages of the slaughter weight.

How did you calculate the feed conversion ratio?

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proximate constituents of the treatment diets, used in this study are presented in Table 2. The values for the cassava peel fell within the range reported by Okereke (2003), Ahamefule *et al.* (2000) and Ukanwoko (2007). The proximate constituents of the oil palm leaf meal were within the values obtained by Esonu *et al.* (2008) and Wong and Zahari (1992). The crude protein percentage of the diets tended to increase as the level of inclusion of oil palm leaf meal increased from treatments I to III. The crude fibre contents of the treatment diet followed the same trend as the crude protein. The ash content was highest in treatment II followed by treatment I and treatment III. The ether extract content of the treatments followed the same trend. The nitrogen free extract values do not follow any consistent trend among the treatments.

Table 3 shows the performance of WAD goats fed oil palm leaf meal – cassava peel based diets. There were significant differences ($P < 0.05$) in the final weight of goats fed the treatment diets. The final weight of goats on treatment III was highest (10.67 kg) while goats on treatment I had the lowest (8.63 kg). The highest weight in treatment III was an indication of better acceptability and protein contribution of the diet (Anigbogu 2007). The feed intake was significantly different ($P < 0.05$). The highest feed intake was in treatment III (394.20 g/d), followed by treatment I (367.40 g/d) and treatment II (367.00 g/d). Feed intake has been observed to be governed by dietary crude protein, palatability and other factors like gut fill, body fat and changes in the body chemical constituents (Ahamefule 2005; Ukanwoko 2007). There were significant differences ($P < 0.05$) in the total body weight gain values of the goats. The highest was in treatment III (2.17 kg) and the lowest was in treatment I (1.50 kg). The highest total body weight gain was as a result of better utilization of the nutrients in the diets (Anigbogu 2007). There were significant differences ($P < 0.05$) in the feed conversion ratios. Their values were 12.33, 10.83 and 9.00 for treatments I, II and III respectively. Treatment III had the best feed conversion ratio which invariably translated to higher weight gain. This tended to be in line with what Ahamefule (2005) reported.

Carcass yield of WAD goats fed oil palm leaf meal – cassava peel based diets is presented in Table 4. The slaughter and bled weights were significantly different ($P < 0.05$) among the treatment. The highest were in treatment III. Dressing percentage values were 50.16, 50.83 and 51.12 for treatments I, II and III respectively. There were significant differences ($P < 0.05$) among the treatment groups. Dressing percentage was highest for

goats on treatment III. The values were within the range of 50.4 – 52.6% reported by Ahamefule (2005) and a percentage of 50% reported by Hassan and Idriss (2002). The meat cuts were expressed as percentage of slaughter weight. There were significant differences ($P < 0.05$) in the values of the leg in the different treatments. Treatment III recorded the highest percentage and the lowest was recorded in treatment II. The range of 10.26-12.30% leg in this study compared favourably with the range of 9.47- 10.43% reported for WAD goats by Ukanwoko (2007). The offal weights were expressed as the slaughter weight. The weight of the head, skin and full gut were significantly different ($P < 0.05$). The weights ranged from 10.19 to 10.73% with a mean of 10.46% for the head, 8.29 to 8.95% with a mean of 8.62% for the skin and 29.53 to 33.92% with a mean of 31.73% for the full gut. These are comparable with what had earlier been reported for WAD goats (Ahamefule 2005; Ukanwoko 2007). The organ weights did not differ significantly ($P > 0.05$). This implies that the weights of the kidney and liver were not affected by the presence of cassava peels and oil palm leaf meals in the treatment diets. The anti – nutritional factors contained in the cassava peels and oil palm leaf meals might have been reduced to a tolerable level by sun drying (Akinmitimi 2004).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Generally, the incorporation of oil palm leaf meal in cassava peel based diets improved nutrient intake, average daily weight gain, feed conversion ratio and dressing percentage in WAD goats. The 30% oil palm leaf meal diet (treatment III) promoted better dressing percentage therefore, it is ideal for fattening WAD goats. From this study, goats can be fattened to market weight within 56 days thereby increasing the income of the farmer. It is relatively cheap to raise WAD goats profitably using low cost agro – industrial by-products during the period of feed scarcity. This should be extended to the rural farmers who keep most of these animals through extension services to enlighten them to practice intensive rearing of goats. This will make animal protein available to the ever growing population of Nigeria.

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Table 1. Composition of the treatment diets

	Treatments		
	T1	T2	T3
Ingredients(%)			
Cassava peel	66	51	36
Oil palm leaf meal	0	15	30
Palm kernel cake	15	15	15
Brewers' dried grain	10	10	10
Soya bean meal	5	5	5
Bone meal	3	3	3
Common salt	1	1	1

Table 2. Proximate composition of the experimental diets, cassava peels and oil palm leaf meal

	Treatments				
	T1	T2	T3	OPLM	CP
Constituents(%)					
Dry matter	88.69	88.54	89.72	90.68	89.82
Crude protein	9.04	10.74	12.02	16.24	6.38
Crude fibre	15.71	17.29	19.45	16.29	24.66
Ash	18.27	20.34	16.73	11.35	18.16
Ether extract	1.06	1.12	1.04	3.14	6.6
Nitrogen free extract	60.34	56.34	59.93	59.95	40.40

Where OPLM is Oil palm leaf meal, CP is cassava peel

Table 3. Performance of West African Dwarf goats fed oil palm leaf meal – cassava Peel based diets.

Parameters	Treatments			
	T1	T2	T3	SEM
Initial bodyweight(kg)	7.83	7.70	8.20	0.33
Final bodyweight(kg)	8.63 ^b	8.80 ^b	10.67 ^a	0.35
Mean bodyweight(kg)	8.10 ^b	8.00 ^b	9.60 ^a	0.31
Feed intake(g/d)	367.40 ^b	367.00 ^b	394.20 ^a	6.70
Total bodyweight gain(g/d)	1.50 ^b	1.67 ^b	2.17 ^a	0.14
Bodyweight gain(g/d)	30.60 ^b	34.03 ^b	44.23 ^a	2.77
Feed conversion ratio	12.33 ^a	10.83 ^b	9.00 ^c	0.99
Feed cost(kg/₦)	15.00	15.00	15.00	
Total cost of feed consumed(₦)	236.73	269.77	289.77	22.33
Feed cost / unit gain	185.46	162.47	134.83	14.62

^{ab}Means on the same row with different superscripts differ significantly (P<0.05)

Table 4. Carcass yield of WAD goats fed oil palm leaf meal – cassava peel based diets.

Parameters	Treatments			
	T1	T2	T3	SEM
Slaughter weight(kg)	8.23 ^b	8.40 ^b	10.23 ^a	0.35
Bled weight(kg)	7.73 ^b	7.90 ^b	9.83 ^a	0.33
Warm carcass(kg)	4.12	4.27	5.23	0.13
Dressing percentage (%)	50.16 ^b	50.83 ^b	51.12 ^a	0.37
Meat cuts (expressed as % of slaughter weight)				
Leg	10.33 ^b	10.26 ^b	12.30 ^a	0.49
Loin	8.20	8.64	8.46	1.03
Sets	8.14	8.15	8.78	0.98
Ends	3.40	3.3	2.39	0.53
Shoulder	13.17 ^b	13.11 ^b	14.15 ^a	0.35
Abdominal fat	0.89	0.87	0.84	0.01
Offal weights expressed as % of slaughter weight				
Head	10.73 ^a	10.19 ^b	10.26 ^b	1.60
Skin	8.95 ^a	8.29 ^b	8.47 ^b	0.79
Feet	3.29	3.60	2.40	0.63
Full gut	29.53 ^b	30.36 ^b	33.92 ^a	0.06
Empty gut	6.74	6.99	7.01	1.37
Organ weights expressed as % of slaughter weight				
Liver	1.19	1.22	1.41	0.23
Kidney	0.35	0.35	0.39	0.09
Heart	0.39	0.38	0.38	0.06
Spleen	0.14	0.12	0.14	0.04
Lungs	0.81	0.75	0.81	0.14
Testicles	0.66	0.59	0.52	0.15

^{ab}Means in the same row with different superscripts are significantly different (P<0.05)

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